

Methodology for Approval of Autonomous Ship System CONOPS

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Abstract

This paper outlines a methodology to describe the concept of operations (CONOPS) of autonomous ship systems. The intention of this methodology is to formalize the activities performed by the various actors in the autonomous ship system, both the ship itself, the remote-control centre, and others. The activities are described in the context of the various voyage phase patterns (cargo operations, berthing, sailing etc) that a voyage consists of and the required ship processes (navigation, cargo handling etc.). The description can be used for approval of the autonomous ship system and for safety and security analysis.

1. Introduction

Autonomous ship systems must be at least as safe and secure as conventional ships. To ensure this, the concept of operation (CONOPS) for an autonomous ship system must be described for each of its areas of operation and for its intended usage. Currently, few formalities exist on how to ensure that all aspects regarding autonomous, supervised, and manual operations are covered.

Currently, autonomous ship systems are approved according to what is described as alternatives and equivalent design as described by IMO, *IMO (2013)*. This can be carried out for ship processes, systems, or components that either directly or indirectly propose alternative ways of compliance with prevailing regulations. For instance, the Norwegian Maritime Authority uses the approach of alternative and equivalent design when approving autonomous ship systems, *IMO (2013)*. This is done in lack of specific regulations for autonomous ship systems; however, IMO has started work on this in their scoping exercise, *IMO (2021)*.

Fig.1: Methodology Overview

An important aspect is that the autonomous ship system must be approved for a certain operation in a given geographical area. This means that a CONOPS is needed, that is, a detailed description of the autonomous ship system's operation. In this paper, we will demonstrate a methodology to formalize these descriptions. The methodology is based on UML (Unified Modeling Language) models describing the use cases and activities, the state transitions and message sequences. Activity diagrams give an overview of the needed operations during a voyage. This means that the autonomous ship system's operation can be described based on formalized templates using UML and then detailing this description to the scenario at hand through several iterations, see Fig.1. This is based on a methodology previously

described in (Rødseth *et al.*, 2021) and (Rødseth, 2021). This paper will give a practical example of application of this methodology for an autonomous cargo ferry crossing the Oslo fjord.

In addition to being used during approval, a formalized description of the operation of the autonomous ship system can be used during testing of the system and the description of the test procedures.

2. Background for the Methodology

2.1 Handover

Constrained autonomy means that the automation systems and human operators must cooperate on more equal terms, and we do not expect the system to be fully autonomous, i.e. a Remote Control Centre (RCC) operator must be available. Further, the RCC operator must trust that the automation is able to notify the operator in time for him or her to get situational awareness and conduct corrective actions in cases where the automation encounters problems. This means that the RCC operator does not need to be available at all times, for instance during the less demanding operations. Also, the automation must ensure that alerts are sent to a human operator in cases when the automation detects that it is not able to handle the situation. If the automation does not get positive response from the RCC operator, the automation must transfer the ship to a pre-defined fallback condition to avoid an unacceptable risk to the ship or environment. The RCC operator can take direct control of the autonomous ship system at any time.

A related concept to the handover between the RCC operator and the automation on board is the accountability of autonomous ship systems as described in Myhre *et al.* (2020). They argue that accountability is an important part of the design of an autonomous ship system, in that a clear description of accountability is needed regarding who is legally accountable for the system, how the hand-over is done, how to ensure that exactly one party is accountable at any given time, and how to handle cases where the accountable party is not able to fulfil its obligations. This can be seen as a formalization of the more equal term cooperation between automation and humans.

2.2 Autonomous Ship System

According to ISO (2021), an Autonomous Ship System is defined as all elements that interact to ensure effective functioning of the autonomous and non-autonomous processes and equipment that are necessary to perform the ship's operation or voyage. This means that the safe and secure operation of the autonomous ship will depend on systems not located on the ship, for instance a Remote Control Centre, its operators and the available communication systems. Further, this means that the description of hand-over between the various parts of the ship system and the accountability of each of the components will be an important design criterium.

2.3 Human-Automation Interaction in Autonomous Ship Systems

The ship system described here is not fully autonomous, meaning that the automation cannot solve all issues without help from a human operator. On the other hand, the ship's automation systems can perform some operations safely on its own, under some well-defined conditions. In addition to this, the RCC operator can take direct control of the ship at any time, while the operator can also trust the ship to notify him in time for getting situational awareness and taking proper action, alternatively going to a fallback state if the operator fails to react in time.

ISO (2021) defines 'automation' as the implementation of processes by automatic means, while a ship system's process or equipment is said to be 'autonomous' if some of its components are designed and verified to be safely controlled by automation with no human intervention. These two definitions lead to the conclusion that automation can be used to provide autonomy, and that autonomy emerges when the system is designed, approved and deployed to be operated without human intervention or supervision for certain periods of time, Rødseth *et al.* (2021).

2.4 Level of Human Control in the Autonomous Ship Systems

ISO (2021) suggests that the level of human control on a process may be divided into three levels:

- C0 is where automation handles the system control task and where a human is not needed at all.
- C1 is where the human has responsibility for some parts of the system control task while the automation handles others, for instance when the automation can handle encountering of one ship at open sea, while sailing in more densely trafficked areas cannot be automatically handled.
- C2 is where the human has the full responsibility for the system control task, and where automation is only assisting or offering advice to the human.

2.5 Level of Automated Control in the Autonomous Ship Systems

The level of automation may also be divided into three levels, ISO (2021):

- A0 is where automation is not able to control the process alone and always requires human attention.
- A1 is the degree where automation can handle some parts of the processes, but not all.
- A2 is where automation can control all aspects of the process and does not need human assistance.

2.6 Degrees of Autonomy

Fig.2 shows the suggested degrees of autonomy when taking into account the level of human control (C0, C1, C2) and the level of automated control (A0, A1, A2).

	C2	C1	C0
A2	OA	AC	FA
A1	OA	AC	
A0	OE		

Fig.2: Degree of Autonomy [from ISO (2021)]

ISO (2021) proposes that these levels can be described as follows:

- Fully autonomous (FA): This is when the ship system is approved for operation completely without operators. Operators may still monitor the system, but they will not need to intervene. This means that the accountability is on the automation system.
- Autonomous control (AC): This is when the automation can control the systems under certain conditions and where humans should be available to intervene when required. The conditions are described by a set of state variables and values. The availability of the humans is described by the response time, Fig.3. This means that the accountability is divided between automation and human, and that this transfer of control and the related conditions for this must be clearly defined. The automation can be trusted in that it will either notify a human operator in time for him to be able to get situational awareness, react and solve the situation, or if this is not possible (the operator does not answer or communication is down), the automation will go to a fallback state.
- Operator and automation (OA): Automation can do certain control tasks and will give assistance, but a human is required to be near a control position so that he or she can supervise the process and

intervene when necessary. This means that the human is the accountable party, and that they do not rely on the automation to notify about the operation. However, the operator will possibly receive alarms from the onboard systems than they must handle. An example here is when the operator is in direct control but that the navigation is done by an autopilot.

- **Operator exclusive (OE):** Automation can only give limited assistance, and the operator needs to be continuously in control of the processes. This means that the human is the accountable party. An example here is when the operator is directly steering the ship.

For this paper, the AC and OA levels are the most relevant, since we do not assume the ferries to be fully autonomous with no operators available, and we also assume that direct control by the RCC operator is only needed in specific cases, and not continuously.

Fig.3 Response time for human operators, (Rødseth, 2021)

2.7 Generalization

When the methodology has been applied for several autonomous ship systems and several operations, this may result in a set of generalized descriptions that can be used as pattern or templates for describing a different concept of operation for a similar autonomous ship system. The lower part of Fig.1 indicates that a set of generalized descriptions as UML diagrams and templates may be used as input for new descriptions of operations. Each voyage phase can be selected from a generalized description, and the specific context, state variables and values and use cases can be fine-tuned to the specific case at hand.

3. Methodology with VesselAI Example

The methodology consists of three main steps to set up the CONOPS, Fig.1, the description of the Context (Section 3.1), the Scenario (Section 3.2) and the Use Cases (Section 3.3). The concept of operation will be specific for each autonomous ship system with its specific context and operational area. However, if descriptions of general voyage phase patterns, processes, use cases and templates are available, they can be used to simplify the specification of a CONOPS for a certain autonomous ship system. The description of the CONOPS can be done through several iterations.

The methodology is exemplified with a scenario from the VesselAI project (<https://vessel-ai.eu/>) covering autonomous cargo ferries sailing between Moss and Horten, crossing the Norwegian Oslo fjord. In this case, a Remote Control Centre will be utilized, with operators having the role of an onshore captain in cases when the autonomous ferries need support, e.g. to recover from a fallback state. The scenario is further described in the following sections.

3.1. Context

The context of the autonomous ship system consists of a high-level description of the system, an overview of the physical characteristics of the ship, a description of the external actors to the system, that is, sensors, automation in port and relevant services, a high-level description of the Remote Control Centre (RCC) being part of the autonomous ship system, and lastly, a description of the communication systems that are used between the various parts in the autonomous ship system, see the left (orange) part of Fig.1. This description is according to what is summarized in the Autoship project report on autonomous ship design standards, Rødseth et al. (2021).

3.1.1 Big Picture

Fig.4 shows a possible route for the autonomous ASKO ferries planned to cross the Oslo fjord between Moss and Horten from 2022. This ship system consists of two ferries crossing the Oslo fjord carrying 16 trucks each on a 50-minute crossing with four trips scheduled each day in each direction. The ferries are unmanned and supervised, as well as monitored and controlled by an operator in a remote control centre in Horten. The ferries are electric, and in each of the two ports, berthing and de-berthing is done by auto-mooring systems, and loading and unloading of the trailers is done with unmanned terminal tractors. The containers are picked up by electric, manned trucks and are delivered to ASKO warehouses on each side. In this description, we will only look into one ferry, meaning that we will not cover the handover between several RCC operators.

These unmanned ferries operate in an area with relatively dense traffic, where manned vessels are sailing both as part of regular short sea operations (up to five car ferries running between Moss and Horten every 20 minutes), traffic in and out of Oslo and Drammen following the traffic separation lane in the middle of the fjord, and also local unpredictable traffic, for instance leisure boats often sailing closer to one of the shore sides. Also note that the ASKO ferries need to cross the track of the car ferries, since the ASKO quay is to the north in Horten, and to the south in Moss, compared to the car ferry quays. Thus, navigating out of port and approaching the port are likely to be the most demanding parts since in this area the ASKO ferries must turn around to leave/approach the port.

Fig.4 shows an example route where the voyage from Horten (west) to Moss (east) is divided into five phases, A for leaving the port of Horten, B when starting the first leg of the crossing, C, when crossing the traffic separation zone, D, when sailing the last leg, and E, when approaching the port of Moss.

Fig.4: Example route for ASKO ferries crossing the Oslofjord [from <https://kystinfo.no/>]

The autonomous ship system used as an example in this paper is simplified, and will consist of one unmanned ferry, sensors onboard and onshore, and an operator available in the RCC. The RCC operator will have available automatic monitoring equipment similar to that used for Vessel Traffic Services (VTSs), in addition to functionalities especially developed for the operation, supervision and monitoring of unmanned ships. This will be AI algorithms for prediction of the behaviour of the traffic in the area of operation of the ferries, and AI algorithms to predict possible conflicts with other traffic at earlier stages than usual, to be able to reduce the number of evasive manoeuvres for the ferry.

3.1.2 Physical Characteristics of Ship

The ASKO ferries has a capacity of 16 Euro trailers. Length is 67.4 m, beam 15 m and draught 3.7 m. Service speed is 8 kn and max speed is 10 kn, meaning that the crossing between Moss and Horten will

take about 50 minutes. The battery capacity is 1.85 MWh which ensures fully loaded sailing for 4 h at 8 kn. The loading/unloading time is 65 minutes.

3.1.3 Actors

Each of the central actors in the autonomous ship system must be described. This includes the level of automation, level of human control, and degree of automation, according to Section 2.4, 2.5 and 2.6. It can be useful to start with a set of actors described in UML and then select the actors from these. Examples are actors for sensors and various communication means.

The two main actors in the ASKO autonomous ship system are the Remote-Control Centre (RCC) operator and the Autonomous Onboard Controller (AOC), Fig.5.

The RCC will have functionalities such as:

- Remote control, monitoring and operation of the ship
- Handling exceptions
- Follow-up activities during the voyage, e.g. contact with other vessels, ports, government, etc.
- Planning of maintenance, schedules and voyages
- Cargo management such as contact with cargo providers, customers, terminal workers etc.
- Ordering of services, equipment and technologies needed for the maintenance of the ship
- Safety and preparedness activities

The RCC can remotely operate or take control of the ships and perform the connection with other conventional ships, possibly other RCCs, Vessel Traffic Service (VTS) centres or others that require information from the ASKO ferry. This includes information exchange with the ports and requires awareness about the communication availability and integrity between the RCC and the ferry to ensure that the accountability is correctly handled, *Myhre et al. (2020)*.

An important part of the RCC tasks related to the ASKO ferries, is to utilize tools based on AI algorithms to predict the routes for all manned vessels surrounding the unmanned ASKO ferry. The purpose of this is to improve the situational awareness for the RCC Operator during the ASKO ferry voyages and also to reduce the number of evasive manoeuvres needed during the voyage. Better predictions of the behaviour of the nearby traffic should reduce the number and severity of critical situations that the ferries run into. Also, in VesselAI, work is performed to improve the planning of the route that the ASKO ferries will take on their voyage between Moss and Horten, and especially to calculate the optimal starting time for the voyage. When the best possible time slot for the voyage is selected based on the predicted nearby traffic, the number of cases where hand-over by the RCC operator is needed, will be held at a minimum. Likewise, the number of cases where the ferries need to go into fallback states, may also be held at a minimum.

In addition to this comes the possibility for the VesselAI-tools to conduct anomaly detection, meaning that the system can detect that the nearby traffic is diverging from their predicted behaviour.

The AOC will have the following tasks:

- Interact with onboard systems to execute the autonomous operations
- Interact with external sensors and systems, for instance external infrastructure, which may be shore-based or land-based, weather data from sensors and navigational aids from external sources for instance lidars in the port used for positioning during berthing and de-berthing
- Interact with other vessels
- Interact with VTSS, e.g. sending current route plan
- Report real-time information to the RCC
- Calculate own capacities based on internal factors (own capacity, propulsion system, ballast

and trim, technical condition, power production) and external factors (fairway conditions, weather, traffic, geography, digital infrastructure)

- Validate the communication link between the ship and the RCC

In a testing phase, the ASKO ferries will be operated from a RCC in Horten with crew onboard. When the testing and approval is finished, the ASKO ferries will operate unmanned.

Fig.5 shows that both the RCC and the AOC can access the onboard systems and that the RCC and the AOC must communicate directly to be able to handle the accountability of the whole autonomous ship system. Also, both the RCC and the AOC must interact with external actors. The external actors include:

- Autonomous terminal tractors that are used for roll-on and roll-off of the trailers from/to the ferries
- Automated mooring system activated from the ferry when it is being moored or is leaving the berth
- Local Positioning System (LPS) which is a more accurate positioning system used in the port to aid in mooring, berthing and cargo operations
- The operation area for the ASKO ferries is covered by Horten VTS, so the RCC Operators need to interact with this.
- Other ships: The autonomous ship system may also have to interact with other ships in the area. This may be through voice for the RCC Operator or via electronic message exchange for the ferry.

Fig.5: Autonomous Ship System

3.1.4 Communication Systems

The communication between the RCC and the ASKO ferries will need to have relatively high bandwidth for remote control of the ferries, typically via internet protocols over mobile data, for instance MBR (Maritime Broadband Radio, <https://www.kongsberg.com/no/maritime/products/bridge-systems-and-control-centres/broadband-radios/maritime-broadband-radio/>).

For communication between the ferries and the mooring system, dedicated short range and real-time lines for direct control is need. These may have lower requirements to the bandwidth required but high demands on low latency and jitter.

3.2. Scenario

The operation itself is described as a scenario containing a voyage including its voyage phases and the sequence of each phase, see middle (green) part of Fig.1 and further description in Section 3.2.2. Also, the ship processes that are needed to control the ship in its various operations, need to be described, see Section 3.2.3.

3.2.1 Voyage

The big picture description of the context is formalized in an UML activity diagram as shown in Fig.6. This shows a possible, overall UML activity diagram for an ASKO ferry operating between Moss and Horten. Each of the activities must be further described and detailed with several other UML diagrams.

Fig.6: UML Top Level Activity Diagram

3.2.2 Voyage Phases and Sequence

Fig.7 **Error! Reference source not found.** gives an example of how a voyage from Horten to Moss with the ASKO ferries can be described by a sequence of voyage phases.

Fig.7: ASKO Ferry voyage phases

The voyage phases shown in Fig.7 can be generalized into voyage phase patterns, Fig.9: Automatic Cargo Loading/Unloading, Deberthing, Berthing, Easy sailing, Complex sailing, and Port Navigation.

The actual voyage phases must be detailed for the specific scenario. In some cases, templates for these descriptions can be used as an initial description, and then updated with the specific requirements.

3.2.3. Ship Processes

Fig.9 shows the two most relevant ship processes for the ASKO scenario, namely Navigation and Cargo Handling. For navigation, the following is important processes for this scenario, *Rødseth et al. (2021)*:

- Situational awareness, that is, to verify the location, observe weather and sea, determine visibility, detect and classify objects and obstacles and assess own ship and the traffic situation.
- Manoeuvring the ship, that is, to do short term planning of safe operations, keep track, speed and course, avoid obstacles and avoid grounding, operate automation systems, for instance acknowledge that an auto-mooring-operation can start, or do manual berthing or deberthing when the operational state makes it impossible to do this automatically, and interaction with other actors during manoeuvring, for instance other ships or the VTS.
- Voyage management, that is, planning and re-planning of the voyage done by the RCC operator based on the prediction algorithms for the traffic during a possible crossing and prediction of the route for the ASKO ferry, do pre-departure and pre-arrival checks, monitor voyage and act on deviations that are not handled by the ASKO ferry by itself.
- Communication during voyage, that is, communication involving other ships, RCC and VTS.

The cargo handling for the ASKO ferries will be done by automatic trucks moving the trailers on and off the ferry. After the trailers have been placed on the quay, they are picked up by manned electric trucks driving the trailers to their destination.

Other ship processes not shown in Fig.9 may include deck operations, cargo, stability, hull integration, machinery and technical systems, security, safety and emergency management, environmental protection and maintenance, ship administration and planning.

3.3. Use Cases

The third part of the methodology is the description of Uses Cases, see right (blue) part of Fig.1. Each use case is described by a State Space, Section 3.3.1, and some Ship Control Tasks, Section 3.3.3. Each ship control task can span several voyage phase patterns and may be automatic (indicated with green colour in Fig.9 or semi-automatic (indicated with orange). Black colour indicates that the combination of ship process and voyage phase is not relevant.

Fig.9 shows how a set of Ship Control Tasks can be defined for a set of ship processes and voyage phases. For each use case, the State Space is described by text, and the Ship Control Tasks is described by various UML diagrams and related textual descriptions. Use case diagrams for each Ship Control Task will cover UML diagrams for:

- Activities, including fallback activation
 - UML Activity diagrams for the overall description of each ship control task, Fig.10.
 - UML State diagrams for detailed activity description, Fig.11.
- Transfer of Control describing the human-automation interface: The "accountable" actors are actors that can make an independent operative decision, i.e. either a human or automation that is qualified as autonomous. Transfer of control describes the transfer of accountability between actors in a specific ship control task.
 - UML Collaboration diagrams: For the ASKO scenario, this is indicated in Fig.12.
- Communication describing the information flow between actors to be able to assess the safety and security for the communication systems.
 - UML Sequence diagrams, Fig.13.

3.3.1 State Space

The state space for each ship control task is described by a set of variables used to describe the condition under which the ship system will operate in this use case. Typical variables may be:

- Level of human control (C0, C1, C2) for the actors in the autonomous ship system, e.g.
 - Availability of the RCC Operator
 - Ability of the RCC Operator to get situational awareness
 - Response time for the RCC Operator
 - Possibility to divide responsibility between human operators and automatic systems.
 - Human control needed during cargo operation
 - Human control needed during mooring operation
- Level of automation (A0, A1, A2) for each actor in the autonomous ship system including the ship, the mooring system, and terminal tractors.
- Operator response time in the cases where an automatic actor in the autonomous ship system is in direct control, but control is needed to be handed over to a human.
- Traffic condition, e.g. density of traffic and type of traffic
- Geographic or fairway conditions, e.g. whether the voyage is in open waters or in a narrow channel.
- Operational status:
 - Own ship condition, e.g.:
 - Condition of the ship and its manoeuvrability
 - Availability of ship sensor data (e.g. position data, radar, cameras)
 - Availability of communication
 - For berthing, condition of mooring system, and ship's ability to communicate with this
 - For cargo operations, condition of the terminal tractors picking up and delivering the trailers and their possibility to support automatic loading and unloading
 - For cargo operation, status (e.g. ready for loading/unloading) of cargo onboard or on shore
 - Availability, range and status for external sensors:
 - Sensors during sailing (radars, cameras)
 - Sensors during berthing and deberthing (eg. local positioning system as lidar, cameras)
 - Terminal status e.g. quay is free to start the unloading operation
- Weather situation (wind, current, waves)

For the ASKO ferries, the state space can be described by the variables as shown in Fig.8. These are some examples, meaning that more variables are needed for a complete description, and also more details regarding the actual values.

Voyage Phases	Degree of autonomy	Operator response time T_{DL}	Traffic condition	Geographic conditions	Operational status	Weather	Voyage Phase Pattern
Automatic Cargo Loading, Horten	Autonomous control (AC)	1 min, operator available, and takes over if notified by automation.	NA	NA	Check if cargo and autonomous trucks are available for loading	NA	Automatic Cargo Handling
Automatic Deberthing, Horten	Autonomous control (AC)	1 min, operator does monitoring, and takes over if notified by automation.	NA	NA	Direct control if no lidar for local positioning	Direct control by operator needed if wind > 10 m/s	Deberthing
A. Leaving port, Horten	Autonomous control (AC)	1 min, operator	Medium traffic	NA	Direct control if camera detects	Direct control by	Port Navigation

Voyage Phases	Degree of autonomy	Operator response time T_{DL}	Traffic condition	Geographic conditions	Operational status	Weather	Voyage Phase Pattern
		available, and close monitoring	density, high traffic complexity		unidentified objects	operator needed if wind > 10 m/s	
B. Easy sailing	Autonomous control (AC)	5 min, operator available, but monitoring not needed, automation can be accountable party	Low traffic density, low traffic complexity	NA	Tactical control if CPA must be changed	Direct control by operator needed if wind > 18 m/s	Easy sailing
C. Complex sailing	Autonomous control (AC)	2 min, operator monitoring and is always the accountable party	Medium traffic density, low traffic complexity	NA	Direct control in case evasive manoeuvre is needed	Direct control by operator needed if wind > 18 m/s	Complex sailing
D. Easy Sailing	Autonomous control (AC)	5 min, operator available, but monitoring not needed	Low traffic density, low traffic complexity	NA	Tactical control if CPA must be changed	Direct control by operator needed if wind > 18 m/s	Easy sailing
E. Approaching Port, Moss	Autonomous control (AC)	1 min, operator available, and close monitoring	Medium traffic density, high traffic complexity	NA	Direct control if camera detects unidentified objects	Direct control by operator needed if wind > 10 m/s	Port Navigation
Automatic berthing, Moss	Autonomous control (AC)	1 min, operator does monitoring, and taking over if notified by automation.	NA	NA	Direct control if no lidar for local positioning	Direct control by operator needed if wind > 10 m/s	Berthing
Automatic cargo unloading, Moss	Autonomous control (AC)	1 min, operator available, and taking over if notified by automation.	NA	NA	Check if cargo and autonomous trucks are available for unloading	NA	Automatic Cargo Handling

Fig.8: Example state space for ASKO ferries

3.3.2 Voyage Phase Patterns

After specifying each of the voyage phases that the voyage from Horten to Moss consists of, generalizations may be done into voyage phase patterns covering two or more of the voyage phases. This will be based on the actual voyage phases described and also the state space for each voyage phase and ship process. The rightmost column in Fig.8 lists the voyage phase pattern that each voyage phase in the Horten-Moss crossing can be generalized into.

3.3.3 Ship Control Tasks

The ship processes described in Section 3.2.3 and the voyage phase patterns from Section 3.3.2 give us the five Ship Control Tasks (SCTs) as shown in Fig.9.

		Voyage Phase Patterns					
		Automatic Cargo Loading/Unloading	Deberthing	Berthing	Easy sailing	Complex sailing	Port Navigation
Ship Processes	Navigation		UCS1 Navigation during berthing/deberthing		USC2 Navigation during easy sailing	UCS3 Navigation during complex sailing	UCS4 Navigation during port approach and leave
	Cargo Handling	UCS5 Autonomous cargo handling					

Fig.9 Example Ship Control Tasks for ASKO ferries crossing the Oslofjord

Fig.9 gives an overview of the different use cases that realize the ship control tasks for each ship process and voyage phase pattern. In this example, we have selected navigation and cargo handling as the most relevant processes. The rest of this paper shows example UML diagrams to describe the Ship Control Task for navigation during automatic berthing and deberthing (UCS1 in Fig.9).

Fig.10 shows the overall UML activity diagram for the ASKO autonomous ship system for the navigation process during automatic berthing and deberthing where the RCC operator is available. This diagram shows that the berthing/deberthing starts in an automatic mode by checking the connection to the auto-mooring system, checking the physical mooring conditions and by validating the position by the local positioning system. When initialization is OK, the automation onboard will keep track, speed and heading to/from quay until finished. If problems are encountered that cannot be solved by the automation onboard, the RCC operator is requested to take direct control.

Fig.10: UML Activity diagram for UCS1 Navigation during berthing/deberthing

Fig.11: UML State diagram for UCS1 Navigation during berthing/deberthing

Fig.11 shows the UML state diagrams for the AOC, the auto-mooring system and the RCC operator during navigation to and from the quay. The AOC is in state berthing/deberthing until the ferry is safely moored or has left the quay, or until some problems have occurred which may trigger a fallback state. Further the AOC goes in idle state when the berthing/deberthing is finished or when the RCC operator has taken direct control. The fallback situation is solved either by the RCC operator taking direct control or the problem has been solved by the AOC itself or the auto-mooring system.

Fig.12: UML Collaboration diagram for UCS1 Navigation during berthing/deberthing

Fig.13: UML Sequence diagram for UCS1 Navigation during berthing/deberthing

Fig.12 shows a simple UML Collaboration diagram for the interaction between the state machines for the RCC Operator, the AOC, the auto-mooring system and external sensors. This diagram shows that the berthing/deberthing is initiated by the AOC, but also that the AOC is dependent of the clearance from the auto-mooring system to start and continue the operation. The RCC operator can at any time take direct control without asking the AOC, however, the AOC must be notified about this. Also, the AOC can request the RCC operator to take direct control in cases where problems have occurred.

Fig.13 shows an UML sequence diagram describing the interaction between the RCC operator, the AOC, the auto-mooring system, the Local Positioning System and some external sensors during navigation to and from the quay. This diagram can be used as a starting point for describing possible vulnerabilities of the communication between the various actors and the effect of this. This sequence diagram is divided into the following: Initialization of the auto-mooring system, message exchanges during operation, finalization of the berthing/deberthing, and handling of error conditions.

4. Conclusion and Further Work

This paper has given an example of how our proposed methodology can be applied on a relatively simple ferry operation. The method is still under development and results from applications on several projects, including VesselAI, will be used to improve it.

A main purpose of the methodology is that the use of UML in the design process also can be used in analysis, verification and approval of the systems. As was mentioned earlier in the paper, the methodology also emphasizes generalization of ship control tasks and their capability envelope, so that reuse of already approved ship control tasks in new scenarios can be greatly simplified.

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